

The Effect of Mental Accounting and Financial Literacy on Green Consumption Behavior among Indonesian Gen Z

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Abstract: Green consumption is an important part of environmental sustainability, climate action, and responsible development. Buying eco-friendly products is seen as a keyway to support long-term ecological health. However, there is little research on how financial thinking alone affects eco-friendly buying, especially in fast-growing countries like Indonesia. This study examines some factors that influence green consumption and spending behavior among Generation Z in Indonesia. This research explores how mental accounting and financial literacy affect their behavior, while also focuses on the role of financial management and environmental attitudes in the process, by using a survey. The findings of this research show that good financial knowledge does not always lead young people to buy eco-friendly product. It usually happens when their concern for the environment is still low. Mental accounting can help them organize their money. On the other side, it also makes them less willing to spend on green products since these products are often more expensive. Finally, this research shows that even young people who have better understanding in finance, still prefer to spend their money on short-term needs or desires rather than making choices that support the environment. Adding ecological awareness to national financial literacy programs could help close the gap between knowledge and action, promote sustainable consumption, and support green development goals.

Keywords: Mental Accounting, Financial Literacy, Financial Management Behavior, Environmental Attitude, Green Consumption, Consumptive Lifestyle

1 Introduction

As the global climate crisis intensifies, sustainable consumption has become a key goal. Indonesia, home to one of Southeast Asia's largest youth populations, faces the challenge of growing its economy while protecting the environment. Although Generation Z is often seen as environmentally aware, there is a clear gap between their knowledge and their shopping habits. Researchers refer to this as the "green gap" (Wang et al., 2022; Pandoy et al., 2025). The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) examines that an intention of a person is shaped by their attitudes, social norms, and the feeling that they are able to control their own actions. However, in real life, people do not always act based on what they intend to do. There are many external factors contributed to their choices. Although financial literacy among young people continues to improve, it does not always make them spend less. Generation Z tend to overspend their

budgets and face higher credit risk, since the digital financial services are accessible nowadays. (Kurniasari et al., 2023; GFLEC, 2024). In the theory of behavioral economics, financial decisions are not always logically made. Their decisions often influenced by what called as cognitive biases. For instance, a mental accounting concept. This concept refers to the financial psychology that explores how people organize their money and control their impulsive buying (Cahyatullah & Hambali, 2024; Firmansyah et al., 2025; Skwara, 2023). Even if people financially rational, it does not mean they are automatically adapt he concept of green consumption. The factors that contributed to people's decision to but eco-friendly products are their attitudes toward environment and the way they manage their money. In TPB, it is examined that even when people have intentions to buy eco-friendly products, their financial situation may prevent them. It is because green products tend to be less affordable. This condition can create self-control problems and

financial stress (Humaidi et al., 2020; Siswanti & Halida, 2020). Therefore, Liu et al (2020) and Szulc-Obłoz & Żurek (2024), stated that strong environmental attitudes are necessary so that a good financial management can support the eco-friendly behavior. This study aims to examine why financial rationality does not always make Generation Z in Indonesia to practice green consumption. This study focuses on how mental accounting, financial literacy, financial management, and environmental attitudes work together in explaining the gap between environmental concern and actual green purchasing behavior, by using behavioral economics and the Theory of Planned Behavior as the main foundation.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Behavioral Economics Theory

Behavioral Economics Theory combines economics and psychology to explain how people make decisions in daily life. Unlike traditional economics, which assumes people are fully rational, this theory argues that decisions are often influenced by emotions, habits, personal perceptions, and social factors. One of its key contributors, Richard H. Thaler, introduced the concept of mental accounting, which describes how people categorize money into different purposes such as daily expenses, savings, entertainment, or special purchases. Mental accounting affects spending behavior because people tend to treat money differently depending on its intended use. As a result, financial decisions are not always based solely on rational considerations.

In this study, Behavioral Economics Theory helps explain how Indonesian Generation Z makes green consumption decisions. Through mental accounting, Gen Z may allocate a specific budget for eco-friendly products despite their higher prices. Financial literacy also supports green consumption by increasing awareness of its long-term financial and environmental benefits. This theory is relevant because green purchasing decisions are influenced not only by income but also by attitudes, mindsets, social trends, and digital media. Therefore, mental accounting and financial literacy provide a useful framework for understanding why Gen Z chooses or does not choose eco-friendly products.

2.2 Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), introduced by Icek Ajzen (1991), explains that human behavior is primarily driven by intentions, which are

influenced by three factors: attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Despite being developed decades ago, TPB remains widely used to understand Generation Z's green consumption and financial behavior. Attitude toward behavior refers to an individual's positive or negative evaluation of buying eco-friendly products. Subjective norms reflect social influences from family, friends, communities, and social media. Perceived behavioral control relates to an individual's confidence and ability to perform the behavior, including managing finances to purchase green products. Together, these factors shape behavioral intentions, which subsequently influence actual behavior.

In this study, TPB explains how mental accounting and financial literacy may affect green consumption among Indonesian Generation Z. Positive environmental attitudes, social influences, and financial capability can encourage stronger intentions to purchase eco-friendly products. Financial literacy, in particular, enhances perceived behavioral control by improving individuals' ability to manage and understand financial resources. TPB is relevant to this study because it demonstrates that green consumption is influenced by psychological and social factors rather than occurring randomly. Previous studies show that attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control significantly influence Generation Z's intention and actual behavior in purchasing and using environmentally friendly products.

2.3 Mental Accounting (X1) from a Behavioral Economics Perspective

Mental accounting is one of the key ideas in behavioral economics. Mental accounting refers to the way people view, separate, and control their money on daily lives. Mental budgeting can shape people's behavior, since it is usually dividing their money based on its structure and the use of purpose (Skwara, 2023). For them who are familiar with digital technology, especially Generation Z, it is essential to have a clear budget to keep the stability of their financial and reduce the financial pressure, as discussed by Firmansyah Wijaya A and Rospitadewi (2025). The proper money management, also supports better self-control and helps prevent impulsive spending. Cahyatullah and Hambali (2024) also point out that mental accounting is important for young people because it can reduce impulsive buying behavior

2.4 Financial Literacy (X2) as the Foundation for Financial Decisions

Financial literacy is not only about understanding the financial terms. It includes the understanding of knowledge, skills, and attitudes which can help people manage their money wisely. Nowadays, there is now a tool to measure people's financial literacy among Generation Z. On a global scale, the need for financial literacy is also recognized. Based on a survey conducted by the Global Financial Literacy Excellence Center (GFLEC, 2024), it indicate that people with a good financial knowledge, are tend to be more ready to face economic challenges. In Indonesia, people's efforts to improve their financial literacy have also helped teachers and students make better financial decisions in their daily lives (Satriadi Widiastuti and Suprianto, 2023). In other words, financial literacy plays an essential role in supporting financial well-being. Financial literacy can also be developed through consistent habits in managing money (Nurkhalida Wijaya A and Hermawan, 2025).

2.5 The Mediating Role of TPB-Based Financial Management Behavior (M1)

In the Theory of Planned Behavior, financial management behavior can be connected to perceived behavioral control because it shows how capable a person feels in managing money to reach certain goals. Responsible financial management usually develops over time. It is influenced by financial knowledge, financial attitudes, and personal traits (Firli A and Hidayati N, 2021). Family background also plays a role. For example, parents' income can affect how students in less developed areas manage their monthly money (Wibowo A S and Dewi A S, 2021). Today, poor financial management can be seen in the lack of control over credit card use or the use of digital financial services that may lead to risky spending behavior (Chen F, Yu D, and Sun Z, 2023). On the other hand, people who practice disciplined money management tend to have more stable finances and better long-term life satisfaction, especially among Millennials and Generation Z (Lathiiifah D N and Kautsar A, 2022; Wijaya A and Widjaja I, 2022).

2.6 Green Consumption Behavior (Y1) and its Comparison with Consumptive Lifestyle (Y2)

The interaction between financial and environmental factors leads to a choice between Green Consumption Behavior (Y1) and a Consumptive Lifestyle (Y2). Green consumption refers to the habit of buying products that are considered more friendly to the environment. Public education, economic conditions, and people's concern are several factors influenced the green consumption (Wang Q, Niu G, Gan X, & Cai Q, 2022; Szulc-Obłozza A & Żurek M, 2024). On the other side, a consumptive lifestyle is closely related to the impulsive buying, especially when people purchase items that are currently trending or to gain social recognition. From the view of behavioral economics, the spending behavior of Generation Z continues to increase, especially because digital financial services make purchasing easier. Features such as "pay later" allow young people to buy products immediately without paying the full amount at the beginning. When this spending habit is not controlled, it can lead to the debt risk and create financial pressure for users (Kurniasari F, Abubakar A, & Constansje B, 2023). Strengthening financial self-efficacy is essential to gain financial literacy with more responsible financial behavior and support healthier financial inclusion among young people (Kartawinata B, R Fakhri M, Pradana M, Hanifan N F, & Akbar A, 2020).

3 Methods

3.1 Research Design

This study uses a quantitative approach. This approach aims to examining the relationships between the variables by using the theories (Creswell, 2018). The researcher gathered the data in numerical form and analyzed them by using statistical techniques to examine the proposed hypotheses (Sugiyono, 2022). By using this approach, the study examines how independent the variables are. This approach also aims to examine how Mental Accounting and Financial Literacy, affect the dependent variables, Green Consumption Behavior and Consumptive Lifestyle.

This study also uses a double-mediation model to see how Financial Management Behavior and Environmental Attitude help to explain the relation

between financial knowledge and actual behavior. The data were processed in SPSS using multiple linear regression and the Sobel test to examine indirect effects. These methods were used in order to measure the strength of the relationships among the variables, both directly and through the mediating variables.

3.2 Population and Sample

Population refers to a group of people who have similar characteristics. Because of the similar characteristics, they become the focus of a study. The population of this are the Generation Z in Indonesia. They must be individuals born between 1996 and 2008. The study also uses a non-probability sampling technique, more specifically purposive sampling. By using this technique, the respondents were not chosen randomly, yet selected based on certain requirements that fit the purpose of the research. The criteria are as follows:

1. Indonesian citizens (WNI).
2. People who have their own income or receive regular financial support, allowing them to make financial decisions independently.
3. People who use digital banking services or e-wallets show they take part in digital mental accounting.

To achieve adequate statistical power for the regression analysis, at least 150 participants were needed.

3.3 Data Collection Methods

Primary data was collected via an online survey. Responses used a 6-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Agree; 6 = Strongly Disagree), which was selected to reduce central tendency bias.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

Data examination was performed using IBM SPSS software. Before evaluating hypotheses, the research tools were checked for validity with Pearson's Product-Moment correlation. The consistency of the instrument was tested using Cronbach's Alpha. Before moving to the main analysis, a correlation test was first carried out to see the relationship among the variables.

To make sure the regression model was accurate, several classical assumption tests were also

conducted. The normality of each variable and the residuals was tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. To examine the Multicollinearity, the researcher pay attention to the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance values. Meanwhile, the Glejser test was used to check whether heteroscedasticity existed in the data. The hypotheses were tested using linear regression and path analysis. The strength of the model was then measured through the coefficient of determination (R^2). The significance of each effect was tested using the t-test and p-value thresholds.

4 Result

4.1 Normality Test

Normality testing using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test showed that all variables—Mental Accounting (X1), Financial Literacy (X2), Financial Management Behavior (M1), Environmental Attitude (M2), Green Consumption Behavior (Y1), and Consumptive Lifestyle (Y2)—had an Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value of 0.000, which is below 0.05. This indicates that the data are not normally distributed. Such results are common in social research using Likert-scale questionnaires, where respondents tend to select particular response categories. In this study, the findings suggest differences among Generation Z respondents, particularly between those with higher and lower levels of financial and environmental awareness. Although the residuals of the regression models were also not fully normal, the sample size ($n = 153$) satisfies the Central Limit Theorem, allowing regression analysis to proceed. Moreover, the SEM-PLS approach does not require a normal data distribution.

4.2 Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test checks if the independent variables in the regression model are too closely related. In all models, Tolerance values range from 0.951 to 0.984, and VIF values range from 1.017 to 1.051. Since all the VIF values are below 10, it means that the data do not indicate a serious multicollinearity issue. In other words, the independent variables are not overlapping with each other.

Multicollinearity are not existing between X1, Mental Accounting, and X2, Financial Literacy. Therefore, it is an important finding because it shows that the two variables do not overlap in explaining financial behavior. Each variables have its own role.

For example, Mental Accounting is used to examine how people organize and control their spending. Meanwhile, Financial Literacy focuses more on their understanding of financial concepts. Since these two variables measure different things, each of them can contribute separately to the analysis and help make the regression results more reliable.

4.3 Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity was tested by regressing the absolute residual values (ABSRES) on the independent variables. In the X1, X2 → M1 model, Mental Accounting (X1) significantly affected ABSRES ($\beta = 0.111$; $p = 0.007 < 0.05$), indicating the presence of heteroscedasticity. In contrast, no significant effects on ABSRES were found in the other models (X1, X2 → M2; X1, X2, M1 → Y2; X1, X2, M2 → Y1; and X1, X2, M2 → Y2), suggesting that the homoscedasticity assumption was met.

The heteroscedasticity in the X1 → M1 model may be explained by differences in how respondents apply mental accounting in daily life. Although some individuals are more systematic in budgeting and controlling their finances, this does not necessarily translate into the same level of financial management behavior. As a result, the variation in financial management behavior becomes uneven across respondents. Future studies may address this issue by applying robust standard errors or data transformation techniques to reduce the impact of unequal variance and improve the reliability of model estimates.

4.4 Results of the Inter-Variable Correlation Test

Before proceeding to the main regression analysis, Pearson and Spearman correlation tests were conducted to explore bivariate relationships among the variables. Here is the summary of the correlation findings:

Table 1
Results of the Inter-Variable Correlation Test

Variable Pairs	Pearson's correlation (p-value)
X1 – M1 (Mental Accounting → FMB)	$r = 0,187^*$ ($p = 0,021$)
X2 – Y2 (Financial Literacy → Consumptive Lifestyle)	$r = -0,162^*$ ($p = 0,046$)
M2 – Y1 (Environmental Attitude → Green Consumption)	$r = 0,274^{**}$ ($p = 0,001$)
X1 – Y1 (Mental Accounting → Green Consumption)	$r = 0,002$ ($p = 0,978$)
X2 – Y1 (Financial Literacy → Green Consumption)	$r = -0,036$ ($p = 0,663$)
X1 – X2 (antar variabel independen)	$r = 0,128$ ($p = 0,115$)

Source: Authors' own work

The three main correlation results provide an overview of how the variables are connected to each other. First, Mental Accounting has a significant positive relationship with Financial Management Behavior, shown by $r = 0.187$ and $p = 0.021$. This means that people who are used to separating and arranging their money into different categories, are tend to manage their finances more carefully. In everyday life, this can be seen when someone sets aside money for savings, daily needs, bills, and other expenses.

Second, Financial Literacy has a negative relationship with Consumptive Lifestyle, with $r = -0.162$ and $p = 0.046$. This shows that people with better financial understanding are less likely to live in a highly consumptive way. When individuals understand budgeting, saving, and the risks of careless spending, they usually become more

thoughtful before buying things they do not really need.

Third, Environmental Attitude has a strong positive relationship with Green Consumption Behavior, with $r = 0.274$ and $p = 0.001$. This finding indicates that concern for the environment has an important role in encouraging people to choose eco-friendly products. The stronger someone's environmental attitude is, the more likely they are to consider sustainability when making purchasing decisions.

In other words, the stronger someone's environmental awareness is, the more likely they are to make purchasing decisions that support sustainability. On the other hand, neither X1 nor X2 shows a direct significant correlation with Y1. This result will be checked and further discussed in subsequent regression tests.

5 Discussion

5.1 The Effect of Mental Accounting (X1) and Financial Literacy (X2) on Financial Management Behavior (M1)

The regression results for the first model ($X1, X2 \rightarrow M1$) yielded an R^2 of 0.036, meaning that Mental Accounting and Financial Literacy together account for only 3.6% of the variance in Financial Management Behavior. The F-value with a $p = 0.065$ shows that the model is not significant at the 0.05 level. This means that, the model has not met the standard requirement for statistical significance. However, the result is still quite close to the significance limit. Therefore, it may still show a possible relationship.

Mental Accounting (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Financial Management Behavior, even when each variable is examined separately. It means that people who are better at organizing and controlling their money, tend to show better financial management habits. This is shown by $\beta = 0.139$, $t = 2.260$, and $p = 0.025$. This finding is in line with the Theory of Planned Behavior, which explains that Financial Management Behavior (M1) can be seen as part of perceived behavioral control. In this context, good financial management shows a person's ability to control their money and turn their intentions into real actions. Prudent financial management behavior among the productive-age population does not emerge instantly but is shaped by the accumulation of sound financial knowledge, mature financial attitudes, as well as the individual's own personality characteristics (Firli A & Hidayati N, 2021). In the context of Indonesian Gen Z, who frequently use digital wallet apps such as GoPay, OVO, and Jago, the feature of creating financial "pockets" or "categories" inherently trains mental accounting cognition, which in turn reinforces more planned financial management behavior.

Conversely, Financial Literacy (X2) does not have a significant effect on Financial Management Behavior ($\beta = 0.017$; $t = 0.382$; $p = 0.703$). This finding supports what financial psychology often calls the knowledge-behavior gap. In simple terms, knowing financial concepts does not always mean that someone will apply them in daily money management. The finding is align with a study conducted by Shehata et al. (2021), who stated that financial literacy does not always lead us to better

behavior. In other words, knowing about financial matters is important. Yet, knowledge may not change a person's actions. It needs to be supported by attitude and personal motivation. Among Generation Z, this gap may happen because their financial decisions are not only influenced by what they understand. Social pressure around them also plays a huge role. There are several factors contributed to the impulsive buying. Social media trends, easy access to digital credit such as pay-later services, and the fear of missing out, can encourage young people to spend more than they actually need. Because of the pressures, financial knowledge alone may not be strong enough to control their spending behavior. Even when young people already understand budgeting, saving, and responsible spending, they may still struggle to manage their buying habits. This becomes harder especially when they are constantly exposed by trends and easy payment options.

5.2 The Effect of Mental Accounting (X1) and Financial Literacy (X2) on Environmental Attitude (M2)

The second model, which examined the effect of X1 and X2 on M2, showed an R^2 value of 0.030, with $F = 2.353$ and $p = 0.099$. This means that the model was not statistically significant as a whole, since the p-value was higher than 0.05. In other words, Mental Accounting and Financial Literacy did not strongly explain changes in Environmental Attitude in this model. Mental Accounting shows a positive direction of influence on Environmental Attitude ($\beta = 0.149$; $p = 0.070$) but does not reach the significance level at $\alpha = 0.05$. Financial Literacy also has no significant effect ($\beta = 0.055$; $p = 0.352$).

These findings have intriguing theoretical implications: financial rationality, whether in its cognitive form (Mental Accounting) or as formal knowledge (Financial Literacy), is inherently insufficient to build or alter an individual's environmental attitude orientation. Environmental attitude (M2) is shaped through deeper socialization processes, exposure to environmental information, direct experiences, and values internalized through family and cultural education. This aligns with the notion that environmental attitudes are a manifestation of the attitude component in the TPB, which measures the extent to which individuals support ecosystem protection movements. An individual's environmental knowledge alone cannot directly translate into pro-environmental behavior without the mediation of positive mental attitudes

and a strong behavioral intention (Liu P, Teng M, & Han C, 2020).

5.3 Effect on Green Consumption Behavior (Y1): The Critical Role of Environmental Attitude

The regression results showed a clear difference between the two mediation models. The model with Financial Management Behavior (M1) was not significant ($R^2 = 0.012$; $p = 0.625$), and neither M1 nor the independent variables significantly affected Green Consumption Behavior. In contrast, the model with Environmental Attitude (M2) was significant ($R^2 = 0.080$; $p = 0.006$), with Environmental Attitude emerging as the only significant predictor ($\beta = 0.320$; $p = 0.000$). This indicates that Environmental Attitude plays a stronger mediating role than Financial Management Behavior. The positive coefficient also confirms that stronger environmental attitudes are associated with higher green consumption behavior, consistent with the correlation results ($r = 0.274$; $p = 0.001$).

The findings suggest that green consumption is driven more by environmental values than by financial management skills. While digital financial services increasingly encourage impulsive spending among Gen Z (Kurniasari et al., 2023), environmentally conscious individuals remain more willing to purchase eco-friendly products despite their higher prices. This supports the existence of a “green gap” among Indonesian Gen Z, where financial capability alone does not translate into green purchasing behavior due to insufficient environmental commitment. These results also challenge Rational Choice Theory, which assumes that awareness of long-term benefits will automatically lead individuals to choose green products.

5.4 Effect on Consumptive Lifestyle (Y2): The Specific Role of Financial Literacy

Both mediation models produced similar results and were not statistically significant overall. The model $X1, X2, M1 \rightarrow Y2$ yielded $R^2 = 0.036$ ($F = 1.868$; $p = 0.137$), while the model $X1, X2, M2 \rightarrow Y2$ yielded $R^2 = 0.037$ ($F = 1.923$; $p = 0.128$). Despite the insignificant overall models, Financial Literacy (X2)

consistently showed a significant negative effect on consumptive behavior (Y2). In the model with M1, $\beta = -0.160$, $t = -2.109$, $p = 0.037$, while in the model with M2, $\beta = -0.151$, $t = -1.985$, $p = 0.049$. These findings indicate that individuals with higher financial literacy are less likely to engage in excessive or unnecessary spending.

For Generation Z, financial literacy helps improve financial decision-making, enabling better control over impulsive purchases, wasteful spending, and trend-driven consumption. However, reducing consumptive behavior does not necessarily lead to green consumption. This suggests a behavioral bifurcation, where individuals may avoid excessive spending without choosing environmentally friendly products. Instead, they may prefer saving or investing their money, particularly when green products are perceived as more expensive.

5.5 Mental Accounting: Limited and Specific Effects

Mental Accounting (X1) did not show a significant direct effect on Green Consumption Behavior (Y1) or Consumptive Lifestyle (Y2). A significant effect was found only on Financial Management Behavior (M1) ($p = 0.025$). These findings suggest that Mental Accounting plays a limited but dual role among Indonesian Generation Z. While categorizing money into different mental accounts can improve financial discipline, it may also reduce the likelihood of green consumption. Since eco-friendly products are often more expensive, they may be perceived as non-essential or luxury expenses rather than basic needs.

This finding aligns with the concept of strict mental budgeting in behavioral finance. By allocating money into specific spending categories, individuals may become less flexible in their purchasing decisions. Although they may care about environmental issues, they may avoid buying green products if such purchases fall outside their planned budget. Therefore, while mental budgeting helps control spending, overly rigid budgeting can limit consumers' ability to purchase products that reflect their personal values, including environmentally friendly and sustainable products.

5.6 Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results

Table 2

Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results

H	Hipotesis	Results	p-value / Desc.
H1	X1 (Mental Accounting) → M1 (Financial Management Behavior)	Supported	p = 0,025 (sig.)
H2	X2 (Financial Literacy) → M1 (Financial Management Behavior)	Not supported	p = 0,703 (ns.)
H3	X1 (Mental Accounting) → M2 (Environmental Attitude)	Not supported	p = 0,070 (ns.)
H4	X2 (Financial Literacy) → M2 (Environmental Attitude)	Not supported	p = 0,352 (ns.)
H5	M1 (FMB) → Y1 (Green Consumption Behavior)	Not supported	p = 0,214 (ns.)
H6	M2 (Environmental Attitude) → Y1 (Green Consumption Behavior)	Supported	p = 0,000 (sig.)
H7	X2 (Financial Literacy) → Y2 (Consumptive Lifestyle)	Supported	p = 0,037/0,049 (sig.)
H8	X1 (Mental Accounting) → Y2 (Consumptive Lifestyle)	Not supported	p > 0,05 (ns.)

Source: Authors' own work

5.7 Integrative Discussion: Why Does Financial Rationality Fail to Promote Green Consumption?

Overall, the findings indicate that mental accounting and financial literacy do not directly encourage green consumption behavior. Green purchasing decisions are influenced not only by financial considerations but also by environmental concern, personal values, and a sense of responsibility toward sustainability. Consumers may choose eco-friendly products because they believe their purchases contribute to environmental protection. These results also support criticisms of Rational Choice Theory, which assumes that decisions are driven by logical benefits and self-interest. In reality, green consumption is often shaped by values, emotions, habits, social influences, and environmental awareness, making it difficult to explain solely through economic reasoning.

The study suggests that financial education should be integrated with environmental awareness. While financial literacy improves money management, it may not promote sustainable consumption without strong environmental values. Therefore, governments, financial institutions, and digital financial platforms should develop programs that combine financial literacy with sustainability education, helping young people understand that responsible financial decisions also involve environmentally responsible consumption choices.

6 Conclusion

This study investigates the effects of Mental Accounting and Financial Literacy on Green Consumption Behavior among Indonesian

Generation Z, with Financial Management Behavior and Environmental Attitude as mediating variables. The results show that Mental Accounting positively influences Financial Management Behavior, indicating that individuals who manage their finances systematically tend to make better financial decisions. However, Mental Accounting does not significantly affect Environmental Attitude, Green Consumption Behavior, or Consumptive Lifestyle.

Financial Literacy does not significantly influence Financial Management Behavior, Environmental Attitude, or Green Consumption Behavior, but it negatively affects Consumptive Lifestyle, suggesting that financially literate individuals are better at controlling impulsive spending. Likewise, Financial Management Behavior does not significantly encourage Green Consumption Behavior. Environmental Attitude is identified as the strongest predictor of Green Consumption Behavior. Individuals with greater environmental concern are more likely to choose sustainable products, supporting the Theory of Planned Behavior, which highlights the role of attitudes in shaping behavior. Overall, the findings reveal a “green gap” among Indonesian Generation Z: financial knowledge and good money-management habits do not automatically lead to environmentally friendly consumption.

Therefore, financial education should incorporate environmental awareness alongside financial skills. Policymakers, educational institutions, and financial service providers can also encourage sustainable consumption through green incentives. The study contributes to the literature by integrating Behavioral Economics Theory and the Theory of Planned Behavior, demonstrating that

financial skills must be complemented by environmental values to promote sustainable consumption among Generation Z in Indonesia.

7 Limitations And Future Research

This study has several limitations. First, it used a cross-sectional design, so the data only reflect respondents' behavior at one point in time and cannot capture behavioral changes over time. Second, the study focused only on Indonesian Generation Z who use digital financial services, which limits the generalizability of the findings to other generations and demographic groups. Third, the data were collected through self-reported questionnaires, which may be affected by social desirability bias and may not fully reflect actual behavior. In addition, the regression models showed relatively low explanatory power, indicating that other factors may also influence green consumption behavior. Future research should consider using longitudinal designs to better observe behavioral changes over time. Expanding the sample to include different generations, regions, and financial backgrounds would also improve generalizability. Furthermore, incorporating additional variables such as social influence, income, environmental education, and digital marketing exposure may provide a more comprehensive understanding of green consumption behavior. Future studies may also apply other theories related to sustainable consumption to broaden the analysis.

8 Research Implications

This study gives a theoretical contribution by supporting the use of Behavioral Economics Theory and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) in understanding green consumption behavior. The findings show that being financially rational is not always enough to make people choose sustainable products. Even when people are good at managing their money and understand financial matters, they may still not choose eco-friendly products if they do not really care about environmental issues. Practically, this study shows that financial literacy programs should not only focus on budgeting, saving, managing debt, and controlling expenses. These programs also need to help people understand that their everyday buying, can have an impact on the environment. For this reason, governments, schools, universities, and financial service providers should work together to encourage more sustainable consumption. This effort can be carried out through

environmental education, public campaigns, and digital financial features, such as green rewards, eco-cashback, or other incentives that encourage people to buy environmentally friendly products.

9 Implications Of The Study

The findings show that promoting green consumption among Generation Z cannot be done only by increasing their financial knowledge. It is important to have an understanding how to manage money properly, but it does not always lead young people to choose environmentally friendly products. They also need to develop stronger concern for environmental issues. This awareness can guide them to think more carefully about the impact of what they buy. When young consumers care about the environment, they are more likely to include sustainability as one of their considerations before making a purchase. This study also indicates that building environmental awareness requires support from different sides. Policymakers, educators, and businesses need to collaborate so young people can understand sustainable consumption more easily and apply it in their daily lives. This effort can be done through education, public campaigns, and business practices that encourage environmentally friendly choices in everyday life.

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